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Manufacturing and experimental testing of carbon fiber/epoxy composites using advanced induction heating system

Andrejs Pupurs, Anish N. Kulkarni, Līva Pupure

Institute of High-Performance Materials and Structures
Riga Technical University, Riga, Latvia

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Background

- Electromagnetic induction heating has emerged as an energy-efficient alternative curing method for polymeric composites
- Main advantages: rapid heating rates, local heating, non-contact set-up, energy efficiency.
- Attractive for application in combination with novel resin systems such as fast-curing epoxies and vitrimers.
- Main drawbacks: mainly works only with carbon fibers, limited compatibility with other material systems, non-uniformity of heating/temperature distribution due to high anisotropy of composites.
- Heating mechanisms: dielectric heating, Joule loss heating, contact resistance heating

Becker and Mitschang (2019)

Objective and tasks

Objective

- To study dependency of heating mechanisms on ply thickness and laminate lay-up (carbon/epoxy laminates)
- To analyze micro-structure and damage evolution in induction-cured composites

Tasks

- To design and develop a kinematic induction heating system (3 degrees of freedom)
- To manufacture induction heat-cured and reference oven-cured cross-ply laminates
- To perform mechanical testing and inspection of micro-damage evolution

Development of induction heating system

Base-frame

FLIR A6752sc thermal camera

CNC software-controlled induction coil movement

Live temperature monitoring and data processing

Induction coil power supply and control unit

Pre-study: induction heating of fabrics

- Fabrics: plain weave, twill, spread-tow carbon fiber
- Effect of number of layers
- Effect of vacuum compaction

Plain weave, 90 g/m²
Toray T300 1k

Twill weave, 240 g/m²
Pyrofil TR30S 3k

Plain weave, 90 g/m²
Toray T700 12k

Nr.	Fabric material	Layers	Vacuum	Max. T [°C]
#1	Spread tow, 88 g/m ²	1	x	23°C (RT)
#2	Plain weave, 90 g/m ²	1	x	33°C
#3	Twill weave, 240 g/m ²	1	x	48°C
#4	Twill weave, 240 g/m ²	2	x	77°C
#5	Spread tow, 88 g/m ²	8	On	61°C
#6	Plain weave, 90 g/m ²	8	On	61°C
#7	Twill weave, 240 g/m ²	8	On	83°C

Induction curing of composites

- UD carbon/epoxy prepregs XC130 from Xpreg
- Pyrofil high-strength carbon fibers
- Areal densities of pre-pregs: **150 g/m²** and **300 g/m²**
- Cross-ply laminates **[0/90]_s**, **[0/90/0]_s**, plate size 300 x 300 mm

Manufacturing parameters:

- Pre-preg lay-up, vacuum pressure, induction heating.
- Outer diameter of the induction coil: 150 mm. Temperature monitored using FLIR A6752sc thermal camera
- Reference material plate manufactured with same curing but in an oven

FLIR A6752sc

Temperature and curing cycles

cycle 1

cycle 2

Plate	Material	Lay-up	Max. T [°C]	Curing cycle
#1	XC130, 150 g/m ²	[0/90] _s	60	n/a
#2	XC130, 300 g/m ²	[0/90] _s	100	4 h at 100°C
#3	XC130, 300 g/m ²	[0/90] _s	100	4.5 h at 100°C
#4	XC130, 300 g/m ²	[0/90/0] _s	120	1h at 120°C

- Rectangular coil movement approximately 90 mm/s

Kidangan et al. (2022),
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2022.104338>

Results: Degree of cure analysis

- Plate #2. $[0/90]_s$, 300g/m² 4 h at 100°C

Results: void content analysis (qualitative)

- Estimation of void content by studying polished longitudinal sections of different specimens

Plate #2. [0/90]_s, 300g/m² 4h at 100°C

Plate #3. [0/90]_s, 300g/m² 4.5 h at 100°C

- Significant amount of voids found in induction-heated plates
- Distribution of voids follows heating paths with most of the voids concentrated in the interface between the two regions
- No significant voids were found in reference oven-cured plates

Mechanical test results

- Plate #2. $[0/90]_s$, 300g/m² 4 h at 100°C

- Plate #3. $[0/90]_s$, 300g/m² 4.5 h at 100°C

Glass transition temperature vs elastic modulus

Tensile elastic modulus

Optical microscopy images

Induction-cured, I8 (Plate #1)

Induction-cured, I5 (Plate #1)

Reference (Oven-cured)

Induction-cured, I11 (Plate #2)

Induction-cured, I7 (Plate #2)

Reference (Oven-cured)

Micro-damage evolution

- Plate #3. $[0/90]_s$, 300g/m² 4.5 h at 100°C

- Results for Plate #3 and reference plate are shown.
- Transverse matrix cracks in the 90-degree layers were manually counted at different tensile strain levels using optical microscopy
- Earlier micro-crack occurrence is observed in induction-cured materials, due to increased amount of voids

Conclusions

- Study showed importance of ply thickness and the amount of ply interfaces for induction heat generation.
- Heating temperatures up to 120°C were reached with the present induction system
- Mechanical stiffness of induction-cured material were on par with reference oven-cured material
- The study highlighted the risk of void formation due to local softening which hinders evacuation of air in the curing process. In turn, this promotes earlier transverse cracking

Future work

- The study of micro-crack evolution will proceed focusing on higher strain levels and different lay-ups
- Development of induction heating system will continue by designing adjustable frequency and power output of the induction coil
- Optimization of heat application paths for uniform temperature and degree of cure

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Thank you for the attention!

Andrejs Pupurs
Institute of High Performance Materials and Structures
Riga Technical University
Andrejs.Pupurs@rtu.lv

